

UPISKETCH: THE RENEWAL OF AN OLD IDEA

Rodolphe Bourotte

Researcher, composer

rodolphe.bourotte@centre-iannis-xenakis.org

ABSTRACT

UPISketch is a program for composing sounds with the help of drawing. Its use is simple: we draw sound gestures by defining their melodic contour, like in a classical score. The difference however resides in the fact that pitches are directly drawn, without the need for knowledge of traditional music notation. We use monophonic sounds as sound sources.

1. INTRODUCTION

Using a paper and a pen to represent music has been the fundamental practice in western music for several centuries. Xenakis was among others to search for new ways of representing music, in a more scientific and general way than symbolic solfeggio. The curve, drawn in a coherent time scale (one unit of width representing one unit of time) seemed to be a natural way for a renewal of the technique. In what follows, the different events and processes that led to the creation of the UPISketch application will be described.

2. THE DETERMINING FACTORS

2.1 The Centre Iannis Xenakis

First, when the Centre Iannis Xenakis was established at the University of Rouen, one of the projects we had was to continue the development of the UPIC, in a way close to Xenakis's original idea. This would suppose the following characterisations: the application should comprise its own synthesis engine, making it a self-sufficient tool for producing sound. It should also provide a sufficient level of drawing accuracy, as far as pitches are concerned.

2.2 The software background 2010-2017

Research conducted in 2010 [1] revealed that there were not many propositions, in the music software world, that could compare to UPIX (the UPIC software version that was available on Windows-equipped PCs in 2001).

2.3 University of Rouen

The proximity of the computer science department inspired us some pedagogical attempts to create a new UPIX. Three

teams were set up between 2014 and 2016. These did not achieve results one has come to expect for a standard software product. However, it proved to be a fruitful experience, which fed lots of discussions. For instance whether, notably, we should use Java or C++ for coding. There was an obvious advantage in terms of learning curve from using Java. But, when thinking about real-time sound, numerous voices in the audio pro world were saying that C++ was the only realistic choice.

2.4 The JUCE expansion

When searching for a C++ library that would cumulate the advantages of being open-source, multi-platform, easy to use and containing all the essential building blocks, the Jules Utility Class Extension (JUCE) appeared to be the ideal choice. Since it is now part of some major audio software in the market (Max/MSP, ROLI's Equator synth...), it has also the advantage of being maintained and enhanced on a regular basis, and benefits from a very lively community of users.

2.5 A partnership with the European University of Cyprus

The CIX had the opportunity to collaborate with the European University of Cyprus on a European-funded program, *Interfaces*, under the coordination of the Onassis Cultural Centre in Athens. The specific entitlement was "Urban Music Boxes and Troubadours". We agreed on a goal, that was to create a small application for mobile devices that would be integrated into multimedia terminals available in the streets of Nicosia. The application would give the possibility to draw music, albeit in a more intuitive way than the original UPIC.

3. THE DEVELOPMENT OF UPI SKETCH

3.1 Rethinking music notation

Before the classical notation as we know it, innumerable systems have been experienced, from the babylonians around 2000 BC, the diverse neumatic notations spreading in Europe to the invention of the staff by Guido D'Arrezzo in the 11th century. Indeed, there is also a plethora of propositions in the 20th-21st centuries contemporary music field for metaphorical notation, which we don't deny the importance. Though, the kind of graphical representations we are devising in these lines is univocal and translates objectively a physical value.

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3.2 The specifications

It was quite a process to set up the specifications for UPI-Sketch. The openness of the territory was seen as an incentive. Meanwhile enthusiasm had to be restrained so as to make the goals achievable in the requested time frame (approximately one year). So we decided on the idea of a GUI (Graphical User Interface) dedicated to granular synthesis.

First the idea came from the fact that the size of the waveforms used in UPIC were quite limited (due to realistic hardware restrictions at that time). This size limitation resulted in a rather static sound. This did not mean that composers could not find or create customised solutions (for instance with frequency and amplitude modulation, the use of recorded samples, or extreme graphical richness).

It came also, in a certain way, from practicing classical Digital Audio Workstations: we often face the need to edit pitch and time in our tracks, a task that is not always as fluid as we would like.

In the UPISketch concept, we use source sounds whose duration is typically that of a musical phrase, or even just a note. Having selected one of these source sounds in the file chooser, we can directly draw and constrain its pitch in an absolute way, in the open space of the page. Time expansion or compression will be applied according to the length of the drawn gesture. This way we can manipulate rich sounds, with their own natural (or artificial) evolution.

Furthermore, new controls can be added to the first version, so that UPISketch could evolve from a simple graphical score composer to an intuitive editor for the various kinds of parameters that granular synthesis naturally allows.

3.3 The first milestone

A first step in the development was conducted in April 2017. It consists in an application for testing two components and their combination: pitch analysis and resynthesis. The investigated solution for analysis was PYin, developed at the Queen Mary University in London [2]. For the synthesis, we wanted to stay coherent, for this first version, with the idea of time manipulation, without the help of transforms in the frequency domain. So we tried an implementation of the PSOLA (Pitch-Synchronous Overlap and Add) algorithm [3] [4]. Once we dispose of the pitch markers provided by the analysis, it consists in choosing grains in the original sound, and redistributing them according to the desired transposition and time parameters. The effect of transposition is to shorten or lengthen the duration between two grains. When time is compressed, some of the original grains (there is one of these per fundamental period) are skipped. In the expansion case, some grains have to be repeated. Some details are not discussed here: the way grains are repeated is important for a better result, as is the placement of pitch markers according to local energy maxima. In parallel with this, we made a research on interpolation algorithms for drawn curves. We decided on choosing the centripetal Catmull-Rom spline, in which, among other advantages, control points have the particularity to be part of the curve [5]. We had also to develop code in order to determine local curvature maximum

Figure 1. UPISketch: screen capture of the first milestone.

points in an array of digitised data (mouse coordinates of a drawn gesture, or analysed pitches). [6].

3.4 The second milestone

We had first to integrate all the previous code together. We could obtain a graphical user interface for creating, manipulating gestures, and navigating in the page. Several additions were made as well, like the ability to save a project as an XML file, choose existing sound sources in a file browser, change display settings. A time and pitch grid was setup. We can tweak the horizontal lines per half-tone and the vertical lines per second of this grid. The previous Gesture object was refactored to suit our needs. It holds now, as one of its elements, a polycurve object. This object is composed of the different curves determining the evolution of parameters like pitch or amplitude. We designed also the interface look and feel. Worth mentioning is that in any software project, we are confronted to difficult situations where we need to make decisions on rewriting some parts of the code. This is what happened then: the hard times of refactoring came. Refactoring is the generic term for this operation. The goal is to simplify the code, while keeping its functionalities unchanged. This restructuration can have a big impact on the maintainability and extensibility of the software.

4. THE PUBLIC RELEASE

4.1 The first hands-on workshop

The first real life appearance in the real world is due to the end of april 2018, taking place at the Bank of Cyprus Cultural Foundation, in Nicosia. During three days, groups of children between six and twelve year old from various backgrounds will be invited to use the application.

4.2 Public availability

UPISketch will be available as a free download. The date of release should coincide with the first UPISketch workshops in Cyprus.

4.3 Perspective on further development

Besides different reasons that can determine whether we will be able or not to push this development further, there are lots of obvious improvements that UPISketch could benefit from. Here is a non-exhaustive list:

Figure 2. UPISketch: screen capture of the second milestone.

- cross-platform: provide versions for OSX, Windows and Android;
- soloing a gesture: ability to monitor only the specified gestures;
- layers: we could assign gestures to specific layers to ease the edition of groups of gestures;
- curves for amplitude: with a pressure sensitive stylus, we could draw at the same time the pitch and the amplitude;
- probability curve: new curves could be added to the polycurve object, for describing the evolution of probability distributions for various parameters;
- select, copy, move several objects
- snap to grid option: so that the placement of gestures fit some predetermined grids, in either time or pitch domains;
- tempo change: changing the page duration could imply a time rescaling of all gestures;
- real time monitoring of the page at playhead position

To this list of updates will be added the requests from users, once UPISketch will have been made public. These can be considered as first priority concerns, while we also want to investigate on new possibilities. Indeed, our intention remains also to conduct speculative thought in an open, interdisciplinary spirit.

5. CONCLUSIONS

UPISketch is a new application that allows to compose with complex (monophonic) sounds in a graphical, intuitive fashion. It is autonomous, from drawing to sound generation. At the time of writing, it has not been made publicly available yet, so there is no feedback data available. But we hope that with this kind of tool, the old idea of drawing music will continue to gain ground.

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